

D2.6: Governance Framework for the European Open Science Cloud

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Abstract:

This document outlines an initial draft framework for a stakeholder driven governance and decision-making structure. This will form the basis, of a governance piloting exercise whereby the framework will be co-designed and developed with the community using the draft framework outlined here as a foundation and strawman.

The draft framework outlines: a three-layer governance model consisting of Strategic, Executive and Steering layers, and the interactions and decision flow between these layers; a resource model for the EOSC, and a skeleton outline of the Executive layers role in commissioning and supporting the EOSC resource; an outline of the role and skeleton outline of the structure of the Steering layer in the form of Stakeholder Forums.

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The objective of Work-package 2 is to design and trial a stakeholder driven governance framework with the involvement of research communities, research institutions, research infrastructures including e-infrastructures, and research funding bodies, to shape and oversee future development of the European Open Science Cloud, and to identify appropriate federated governance model(s) and decision-making structure for it.

As part of that objective, this document outlines a framework for a stakeholder driven governance and decision-making structure for an established EOSC (i.e. post 2021), following from the implementation phase governance structure as detailed in the European Commission's staff working document "**Implementation Roadmap for the European Open Science Cloud**"¹. This document also outlines the key differences to be addressed in moving from the implementation-phase governance to this framework, and the reasons behind these.

The following report has been written at the time of the EOSC Portal definition, so it cannot fully reflect on how the Governance framework works viz-à-viz with the EOSC portal and its development as a central function in the EOSC universe. However, this development should be accommodatable within the three pillars of the proposed Executive structure.

The framework outlines:

- A three-layer governance model consisting of Strategic, Executive and Stakeholder layers, and the interactions and decision flow between these layers;
- A resource model for the EOSC, and a skeleton outline of the Executive layer's role in commissioning and supporting the EOSC resources;
- An outline of the role and structure of the Stakeholder layer and its interaction with the Executive.

Figure 1 - EOSC Community Governance Model

¹ http://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/pdf/swd_2018_83_f1_staff_working_paper_en.pdf

2. INTRODUCTION

The EOSCpilot project objectives are to:

- design and propose a possible governance framework for the EOSC and contribute to the development of European open science policy and best practice;
- develop a number of pilots that integrate services and infrastructures to demonstrate interoperability in a number of scientific domains; and
- engage with a broad range of stakeholders, crossing borders and communities, to build the trust and skills required for adoption of an open approach to scientific research

The objective of Work-package 2 is to design and trial a stakeholder driven governance framework with the involvement of research communities, research institutions, research infrastructures including e-infrastructures, and research funding bodies, to shape and oversee future development of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), and to identify appropriate federated governance model(s) and decision-making structure for it (see Figure 2).

Figure 2 - EOSCpilot WP2 Governance Outline

As part of that objective, this document outlines a framework for a stakeholder driven governance and decision-making structure which could be used after the initial implementation phase of the EOSC.

The framework outlines:

- A three-layer governance model consisting of Strategic, Executive and Stakeholder layers, and the interactions and decision flow between these layers;
- A resource model for the EOSC, and a skeleton outline of the Executive layer's role in commissioning and supporting the EOSC resources;
- An outline of the role and structure of the Stakeholder layer and its interaction with the Executive.

Figure 3 - EOSC Community Governance Model

The ideas within this document have been developed in consultation with key stakeholders via a variety of fora including, as well as other workshops and presentations:

- The EOSCpilot Governance Development Forum²
- Stakeholder consultations³
- EOSCpilot Governance Piloting Process⁴
- EOSCpilot Stakeholder Forum events⁵

This document is structured as shown in Table 1, below.

Section	Summary
Strategic Requirements	Outlines the political and policy context for EOSC and the EOSC Governance framework and structure.
Governance Principles	Outlines key principles identified from the community and existing work to which any EOSC Governance framework and structures must conform.
Stakeholders and Resources	Outlines the under-pinning models of EOSC stakeholders and EOSC resources and services.
Governance Model	Outlines the overall model of the Governance Framework.
Governance Structure	Elaborates on the structures with the Governance Model.
Governance Transition	Outlines a transition from the interim Governance structure established by the European Commission for the initial implementation of the EOSC and the longer-term framework described in this document.

Table 1 - Document Structure

This document is intended to become a living document owned by the community. For that purpose, the contents of the most up to date version can be found on github at:

- **Reading version:** <https://europeanopensciencecloud.github.io/Governance/>
- **Editable version:** <https://github.com/EuropeanOpenScienceCloud/Governance/>

² The work of the forum is addressed in deliverables D2.3: *1st Report on Governance Development Forum involvement and activity* and D2.9: *Report on Governance Development Board*. D2.3 is a confidential report, and is currently only available to members of the EOSCpilot Consortium and the Commission. D2.9 was awaiting publication at the time of publication of this report. It will be available from the EOSCpilot website at <https://www.eoscipilot.eu/media/deliverables>.

³ See “D2.1: Draft Stakeholder Map” (<https://www.eoscipilot.eu/content/d21-draft-stakeholder-map>) and “D2.7: Final Stakeholder Map” (<https://www.eoscipilot.eu/content/d27-final-stakeholder-map>).

⁴ See “D2.8 Report on governance piloting process” – awaiting publication at <https://www.eoscipilot.eu/media/deliverables>.

⁵ See <https://www.eoscipilot.eu/eosc-stakeholder-forum-shaping-future-eosc> and <https://www.eoscipilot.eu/events/second-eosc-stakeholders-forum>

3. STRATEGIC REQUIREMENTS

3.1. European Cloud Initiative Communication

On the 19th April 2016, the European Commission published a communication on the “European Cloud Initiative - Building a competitive data and knowledge economy in Europe”⁶. This document outlined the vision of the European Open Science Cloud as:

“The European Open Science Cloud aims to give Europe a global lead in scientific data infrastructures, to ensure that European scientists reap the full benefits of data-driven science. Practically, it will offer 1.7 million European researchers and 70 million professionals in science and technology a virtual environment with free at the point of use, open and seamless services for storage, management, analysis and re-use of research data, across borders and scientific disciplines. Its development will be driven by the scientific community, who are the most advanced users and the largest producers of science in the world. The European Open Science Cloud will be also open for education and training purposes in higher education and, over time, to government and business users as the technologies developed will be promoted for wider application. “

The Communication gives the following requirement for the EOSC Governance structure:

“Create a **fit-for-purpose pan-European governance structure** to federate scientific data infrastructures and overcome fragmentation. The institutional set-up will oversee long-term funding, sustainability, data preservation and stewardship. It will build on existing structures to involve scientific users, research funders and implementers”.

3.2. First HLEG Report

The second key policy document for the European Open Science Cloud is the first High Level Expert Group report published on the 11th October 2016⁷. This makes various recommendations on policy, governance, and implementation to take immediate action on the EOSC in close concert with Member States, building on existing capacity and expertise. Its recommendations on governance are as follows:

1. **Aim at the lightest possible, internationally effective governance.**
Given the urgency and the number and variety of stakeholders and participants required to realise the EOSC, a tightly governed, new infrastructure built 'somewhere' is not the right model for the EOSC to be a success. Instead a more inclusive, flexible, transparent and less centralised approach is required, one that also enables effective global collaboration. The Commission needs to establish a lightweight, sustainable and collaborative governance model for the EOSC for all players to contribute.
2. **Guidance only where guidance is due.**
While we advocate lightweight governance, we need a degree of regulation. For instance, the harmonisation of the current 'standards jungle' needs to be actively coordinated. With no regulation, some major players, public and private, may claim an unjust and counterproductive share in the EOSC. The EOSC will have a myriad of small and very large players, as is the case in the current internet, but it should be perceived by regulators and stockholders alike as a “commons” where citizens, researchers and innovators need to use each other's data and tools in a trusted affordable and sustainable environment. Europe should take a lead in this due guidance element of the Internet of FAIR Data and Services.

⁶ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/communication-european-cloud-initiative-building-competitive-data-and-knowledge-economy-europe>

⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/pdf/realising_the_european_open_science_cloud_2016.pdf

3. Define Rules of Participation⁸ for service provision in the EOSC.

To support wide participation, innovation and sustainability the EOSC needs to be open to all players, public and private, European and non-European and the development of the desired expert infrastructure will be guided and governed by a minimal set of rigorously applied and enforced protocols and developed by parties that endorse so called Rules of Participation (RoP) that specify the conditions under which stakeholders participate. These RoP can be used to brand providers in the EOSC as trustworthy and compliant with the RoP, comparable to Conformant Cloud Providers in the USA. It should be clear that non-EOSC approved players are free to explore any role in the Open Science ecosystem they wish, even if they do not adhere to the RoP. They will just not be able to brand their services as EOSC approved/certified.

4. Federate the gems (and amplify good practice).

Based on the consensus that most foundational building blocks of the Internet of FAIR data and Services are operational somewhere, but that they operate in silos per domain, geographical region and funding scheme, we recommend that early and strong action is taken to federate these gems. Optimal engagement is required of the e-infrastructure communities, the ESFRI communities and other disciplinary groups and institutes. Several of these cross-ESFRI building blocks begin to operate in individual Member States. Simultaneously, the wealth of small and large industrial players in Europe should be engaged. All partners and stakeholders that adhere to standards and sign off on the Rules of Participation (RoP) should be eligible.

3.3. Open Science Policy Platform

In May 2017, the Open Science Policy Platform⁹ adopted a “Report on the governance and financial schemes for the European Open Science Cloud” from its working group on the EOSC¹⁰. This report was submitted to the EU Competitiveness Council. It recommends that:

1. The EOSC should rely on a multi-level and multi-stakeholder governance that ensures a representation for the main stakeholder categories and disciplines, integrating both the national and European levels of authority.
2. Facilitate access to the EOSC across borders and disciplines by carefully analysing all aspects of interoperability (technical, semantic, organisational, legal and policy) and translate them into a common model and rules of participation.
3. European countries and EC should ensure long-term funding of the services that are needed to enable the integration of and access to the resources that can be federated in the EOSC.
4. Different and innovative funding schemes should be investigated to support users to consume services from EOSC-certified providers that are approved based on a commonly-agreed European certification scheme.
5. Kick-off the EOSC ecosystem with enough coordinated financial support from a sufficiently large set of European countries and the EC.
6. Raise awareness and communicate benefits of the EOSC among decision makers, research and education bodies, private sector, industrial and citizen organisations; share best practices and use-cases to highlight the potential and results of the EOSC.
7. Develop Open Science and data skills among all the key stakeholder categories.
8. Ensure to align and develop ethical rules in data management, storage and analytics that are recognized by all stakeholders in the EOSC.

⁸ This concept has been called “Rules of Engagement” and “Principles of Engagement” in previous EOSC communications and reports. The current accepted term is “Rules of Participation” and this is the term used within this document. References to earlier documents have been updated to use this term for consistency.

⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/index.cfm?pg=open-science-policy-platform>

¹⁰ https://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/pdf/ospp_euro_open_science_cloud_report-.pdf

3.4. EOSC Declaration

The EOSC Declaration, published by the EC on 24/10/17 is an outcome of the EOSC Summit of 12th June 2017 that was attended by eighty key stakeholders. The EOSC Declaration sets out key principles on Data Culture and FAIR Data; Research Data Architectures and Services; and Governance and Funding¹¹. The key principles for governance are:

1. **Governance model** - A long-term, sustainable research infrastructure in Europe requires a strong and flexible governance model based on trust and increasing mutuality. As interdisciplinarity is one of the main objectives of the EOSC, the governance model should be based on representability, proportionality, accountability, inclusiveness and transparency.
2. **Governance framework** - The EOSC governance framework will be co-designed, stakeholder driven and composed of three main layers: 1) institutional, including EU Member States and European Commission 2) operational, including a governance board and relevant working committees (e.g. thematic and functional) and 3) advisory, including a stakeholder forum.
3. **Governance board** - A governance board will coordinate the efforts of stakeholders endorsing the EOSC Declaration, with the broad mandate to reach practical agreements for the implementation of an EOSC Roadmap by 2020. The board will have an advisory role and an implementing role of the decisions by Member States and European Commission concerning the programming, financing and towards the setting up of a long-term governance and business model for the EOSC. It will make best use of the outcomes of past and current projects (e.g. EOSCpilot, eInfraCentral and EOSC-hub) and independent expert advice and studies.
4. **Coordination structure** - A coordination structure, funded by Horizon 2020, will help the governance board to manage the implementation, according to agreed rules and methods of stakeholder participation. The structure and its participating entities should be accountable for the responsibilities assumed, based on an objective assessment of their level of readiness in delivering the EOSC main functionalities.
5. **Global aspects** - The EOSC will be European and open to the world, reaching out over time to relevant global research partners. It will increase the global value of open research data and support stakeholder engagement, including researchers and citizens. It will gradually widen the initiative to federated network of infrastructures and nodes from global research partners. The EOSC Stakeholder Forum will have an important role in this sense.

3.5. EC Staff Working Document

The European Commission's staff working document "**Implementation Roadmap for the European Open Science Cloud**"¹² outlines an interim governance structure for the initial implementation phase of the EOSC (see Figure 4). It is envisaged that this can transition to the framework described in this document. This transition is covered later in the document.

¹¹ https://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/pdf/eosc_declaration.pdf

¹² http://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/pdf/swd_2018_83_f1_staff_working_paper_en.pdf

Figure 4 - Staff Working Document - Governance Structure

3.6. Second HLEG Report

The report of the Second High Level Expert Group on the Open Science Cloud (Prompting an EOSC in Practice)¹³ concluded that the provision of resources to support the EOSC will take place in a very heterogeneous landscape of e-infrastructures and service providers, with dispersed users at best aggregated around disciplinary poles and national infrastructures. Addressing this challenge requires the definition of a smallest common denominator, i.e. the Minimum Viable Ecosystem of the EOSC.

Figure 5 - 2nd HLEG Report - Governance Overview

As part of that Minimum Viable Ecosystem, the report supported a Governance structure for the initial implementation of the EOSC (illustrated in Figure 5) very much along the lines advocated in the EC Staff Working Document.

¹³ <https://publications.europa.eu/en/web/eu-law-and-publications/publication-detail/-/publication/5253a1af-ee10-11e8-b690-01aa75ed71a1>

4. GOVERNANCE PRINCIPLES

“Those groups who can affect or are affected by the achievements of an organization's purpose should be given the opportunity to comment and input into the development of decisions that affect them”¹⁴

Stakeholder Engagement: A Road Map to Meaningful Engagement – Cranfield School of Management

A key element of the strategy is the need for the EOsc to be stakeholder driven. It should be “a multi-level and multi-stakeholder governance that ensures a representation for the main stakeholder categories and disciplines, integrating both the national and European levels of authority.” (OSPP Recommendations – Section 3.3). It is therefore important for all stakeholders and all stakeholder roles to be able to participate in the governance.

Moreover, to be “open to all players, public and private, European and non-European” (HLEG Recommendations – Section 3.2), and following the analogies between the development of EOsc and the development of the Internet suggested in the HLEG report, it is also a requirement that:

“No one person, organisation, or company governs the digital space ... Solutions to issues in each layer include policies, best practices, standards, specifications, and tools developed by the collaboration of stakeholders and experts from actors in business, governments, academia, technical, and civil society.”¹⁵

This is encapsulated in discussing the EOsc as a “Commons” – a management theory for natural resources that groups of people (communities, user groups) manage for individual and collective benefit, which through the work of Fuster Morell amongst others have been extended to Digital and Knowledge Commons¹⁶:

*“[The **digital commons** are defined as] information and knowledge resources that are collectively created and owned or shared between or among a community and that tend to be non-exclusive, that is, be (generally freely) available to third parties. Thus, they are oriented to favour use and reuse, rather than to exchange as a commodity. Additionally, the community of people building them can intervene in the governing of their interaction processes and of their shared resources.”¹⁷*

This has led to various proposals to apply the commons principles¹⁸ to research e-infrastructures and open science. The e-Infrastructure Reflection Group proposed an e-Infrastructure Commons in a 2013 white paper¹⁹, which proposes the need for:

“Community building, high-level strategy and coordination in Europe: for each type of e-Infrastructure service, a single coordinating organisation with a central role for user communities. These bodies, in turn, will need a forum for coordination between them across the different e-Infrastructure types.”

This would require strong stakeholder engagement to strengthen governance on the following levels:

- On the **strategic** level user communities should organise themselves to drive the long-term strategy.

¹⁴ <http://www.som.cranfield.ac.uk/som/p15175/Knowledge-Interchange/Guides/Corporate-Responsibility-and-Sustainability/Stakeholder-Engagement-A-Road-Map-to-Meaningful-Engagement>

¹⁵ <https://www.icann.org/news/multimedia/1563>

¹⁶ <http://www.onlinecreation.info/digital-commons/>

¹⁷ Fuster Morell, M. (2010, p. 5). Dissertation: Governance of online creation communities: Provision of infrastructure for the building of digital commons (<http://hdl.handle.net/1814/14709>).

¹⁸ <http://www.bollier.org/blog/eight-points-reference-commoning>

¹⁹ <http://e-irg.eu/commons>

- On the **service provision** level user communities will have to learn to use their joint purchasing power, in a competitive market, which includes both public and commercial offerings.
- On the **innovation** level, advanced users of international e-Infrastructures should participate in the specification and real-life testing of new e-Infrastructure developments.
- On the **standardisation** level user communities should contribute to the process of setting and implementing the international standards necessary to achieve the international, service-oriented, interoperable e-Infrastructure portfolio envisioned for the e-Infrastructure Commons 2020.

EGI and other e-infrastructures expanded upon the e-IRG e-Infrastructure Commons recommendations, extending them to Open Science in general, in a set of white papers and proposals on an Open Science Commons²⁰. These papers and proposals map key principles of Commons management to Open Science²¹ as illustrate in Table 2, below.

Principle of Commons	What it means to the Open Science Commons
Shared resources	Research data, scientific instruments, digital services (including those for data-intensive science), software, written knowledge (e.g., scientific publications, educational and training resources), expertise from people.
Access rights Collective rights, access with no central authority	Access modes are well defined and non-discriminatory for all members of the European Research Area.
Policies Community-based rules and procedures in place with built-in incentives for responsible use, right of access to all according to established community policies	Harmonized access policies, based on one market, clear points of access and support, integrated body of policies for access and use.
Management Community management of communal services and resources	Formally managed services using transparent methods to maintain service access and quality. Management spans organisations to support collaboratively-provided services and is intended to support provision of long-term, high-quality services.
Governance The community of individuals building the commons can intervene in the governing of their interaction processes and of their shared resources.	Governance model with multiple stakeholders, including research communities as producers of knowledge and data, scientific infrastructures, resource providers, national and European scientific infrastructures and e-infrastructures, and providers of the platforms that enable national and Europe-wide sharing (e.g. open source software repositories, training marketplace, service marketplace, identity providers).

²⁰ <https://www.opensciencecommons.org>

²¹ <http://go.egi.eu/oscowp>

Principle of Commons	What it means to the Open Science Commons
<p>Stewardship</p> <p>Long-term, persistent care for a given resource for the benefit of oneself and others (including the resource itself) and collective trusteeship. Caring for the commons means more than just regulating. Caretakers are needed, that is, a system nurturing societal cooperation, sharing of goods and thoughtfulness of generations to come. It entails establishing norms that reduce free riding and hold communities together (community building).</p>	<p>Long-term support of funding agencies to allow for infrastructures to take a long-term view and build for a common European future.</p> <p>A framework of policies and support allows for the growth and development of e-Infrastructure capacity and capabilities.</p> <p>Active maintenance of open science resources, such as technical development, certification of data repositories, and maintenance of training and education programmes.</p> <p>Active effort to increase the amount and quality of knowledge held by the community on required topics such as data preservation, curation and sharing.</p> <p>Regional and national scientific instrumentations are accessible to all, for creation of knowledge, reuse of research outputs and new ways to create scientific data.</p>

Table 2 - Principles of Open Science Commons²²

Both these initiatives can be considered prototypes of the EOSC vision and ambition. The key governance principles, particularly those concerning the involvement of all stakeholders as peers in the decision-making process, are still extremely pertinent. Key principles of Commons which underpin these white papers and which should be observed by any EOSC Governance model can be summarised from Eleanor Ostrom's book "Governing the Commons"²³:

1. Group boundaries are clearly defined.
2. Rules governing the use of collective goods are well matched to local needs and conditions.
3. Most individuals affected by these rules can participate in modifying the rules.
4. The rights of community members to devise their own rules is respected by external authorities.
5. A system for monitoring member's behaviour exists; the community members themselves undertake this monitoring.
6. A graduated system of sanctions is used.
7. Community members have access to low-cost conflict resolution mechanisms.
8. Appropriation, provision, monitoring, enforcement, conflict resolution, and governance activities are organized in multiple layers of nested enterprises.

²² <http://go.egi.eu/oscpw>

²³ Ostrom, E. Governing the Commons. The Evolution of Institutions for Collective Action. Cambridge University Press. 1990.

5. STAKEHOLDERS AND RESOURCES

5.1. Stakeholders

Through the EOSCpilot Engagement activities, we have established a range of different stakeholder who would participate in and would both benefit from and provide benefits to the EOSC²⁴. Any effective governance structure would need to involve and take input from all these stakeholders. The key classes of stakeholder identified with the community is outlined in Table 3.

Stakeholder Group	Description
Researchers	<p>The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) will offer Europe's researchers and science and technology professionals a virtual environment to store, share and reuse the large volumes of information generated by the 'big data' revolution. EOSC, as a functional embodiment of the European Cloud Initiative, will support data-driven innovation and contribute to the creation of a Digital Single Market in Europe. Science and industry will obviously benefit from these developments.</p>
Service Providers	<p>Service Providers are the heart of EOSC's value proposition.</p> <p>Service Providers functioning nationally or at a larger scale, with commercial, non-profit or public status, can have 2 roles in the EOSC: builders or providers.</p>
Research Producing Organisations, Academic Institutions and Research Libraries	<p>Research producing organisations, Academic Institutions and Research Libraries will be the core users of the European Open Science Cloud.</p> <p>Research libraries, archives, academic institutions, university departments and, generally, organisations that are significantly involved in promoting, supporting and enabling research-production activities, play an essential role in the research and scholarship ecosystem</p>
Learned Societies, Research Communities, Scientific and Professional Associations	<p>Learned societies, research communities, scientific and professional associations are key allies to build, use and promote the EOSC</p>
Enterprise	<p>Enterprises relate to the EOSC in multiple ways. EOSC's target group is categorized into a wide range of categories such as Small and Medium sized (SMEs), large enterprises, dynamic European start-ups and entrepreneurs-to-be, researchers, developers, deployers, providers, distributors, etc. Additionally, many sectors can benefit or contribute to the EOSC, for example healthcare, transportation, energy, manufacturing, education, analytics, etc.</p>

²⁴ Detailed in "D8.2: Stakeholder Identification & Engagement Strategy Plan". D8.2 is a confidential report, and is currently only available to members of the EOSCpilot Consortium and the Commission.

Stakeholder Group	Description
Research Infrastructures	<p>The notion of Research Infrastructures refers both to traditional large, physical installations, as well as to distributed facilities which “include networked resources and skill / capacity building initiatives. These resources use advances in information and communications technology and the ‘big data’ revolution to underpin new collaborative methods of research”. Research infrastructures may be based at a single location, distributed across several sites and organisations, or provided via online platforms. Europe hosts several large-scale research infrastructures operating across national boundaries.</p> <p>Research Infrastructures are the base on which the future federated EOSC will be built. They provide several types of services to the EOSC, including data services and expertise. Research infrastructures are often very experienced in providing cloud services to researchers, and as such, are key players in the specification and the set-up of the EOSC. Close cooperation with other research infrastructures and e-Infrastructures within the EOSC will increase the capability of research infrastructures to combine and integrate data and resources in a common environment.</p>
E-infrastructures, VREs and other pertinent H2020 projects	<p>E-Infrastructures, VREs and other H2020 projects are key building blocks of the European Open Science Cloud. The EC Digital Single Market refers to E-Infrastructures as ways of addressing needs of European researchers for digital services in terms of networking, computing and data management. They foster the emergence of Open Science and support the circulation of knowledge in Europe online and therefore constitute an essential building block for the European Research Area.</p> <p>Virtual Research Environments (VRE) help researchers from all disciplines to work collaboratively by managing the increasingly complex range of tasks involved in carrying out research on both small and large scales, and consists of the tools and technologies needed by researchers to do their research, interact with other researchers (who may come from different disciplines, institutions or even countries) and to make use of resources and technical infrastructures available. Some examples of VREs are EVER-EST²⁵, a VRE for research on Earth-science; VRE4EIC²⁶, supporting a multi-disciplinary approach to research on climate change and energy sustainability; D4Science²⁷, a Data Infrastructure hosting over 100 VREs; and BlueBridge²⁸, a gateway to over 60 VREs.</p>

²⁵ <https://ever-est.eu/>

²⁶ <https://www.vre4eic.eu/>

²⁷ <https://www.d4science.org/>

²⁸ <http://www.bluebridge-vres.eu/>

Stakeholder Group	Description
General Public / Citizen Scientists	<p>The EOSC project will create a cross-border and multi-disciplinary open innovation environment with the aim of delivering its benefits to citizens as well. Democratisation of science and open access to scientific data are indirectly providing their beneficial results to civil society. The activities and achievements of the EOSC and open science initiatives need to be linked with the everyday challenges, that citizens are sensitive to, such as public investments, new services and new job opportunities.</p>
National, Regional or Local Government Agencies	<p>Public authorities and government agencies, specifically in their capacity as organisations performing monitoring activities and using research, shall be able to fully exploit the possibilities around Big Data as EOSC will allow them to move, share and reuse data seamlessly across European borders, among institutions and analytical facilities and between different research and data disciplines</p>
Research Funding Bodies	<p>Research funding bodies are key stakeholders for the development of the EOSC. In recognition of this, they were among the first to be involved in extensive discussions with the European Commission's High-Level Expert Group in 2016 with a view to contribute to the initial recommendations on the realization of the EOSC.</p> <p>Several bodies at the European level make research grants available to researchers regardless of their nationality or field of research. This includes programmes supported by the EU under the Research and Innovation Framework programmes – including for example the direct actions of the Joint Research Centre, or the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions or the actions managed by the European Research Council. Other European funding programmes are managed by the European Science Foundation, the European University Institute, the European Association of National Metrology Institutes (EURAMET) etc.</p> <p>Many European countries have one or more national agencies responsible for research, science and/or technology development. The policies and mandates of these agencies will inevitably be different from country to country, but they are essential drivers of Open Science and it is vital for the EOSC to engage in a common platform with these stakeholders.</p>

Table 3 - EOSC Stakeholders

The framework concentrates on three stakeholder *roles*, understanding that different stakeholders can play multiple roles, or different roles are different points in the research lifecycle or within their organisation. These are outlined in Table 4 (the stakeholders listed are indicative and not meant to be exhaustive or exclusive).

Primary Role	Description	Typical Stakeholders
Provider	Provides services, data or other resources (e.g. scientific instruments, training) into EOSC.	e-Infrastructures Enterprises Academic Institutions and Research Libraries Research Infrastructures VREs, and other H2020 Projects Other Service Providers
Consumer	Will make use of services, data, or other resources from EOSC.	Learned Societies, Research Communities, Scientific and Professional Associations Research Infrastructures Research Producing Organisations e-Infrastructures, VRE, and Other H2020 Projects Academic Institutions and Research Libraries Enterprises General Public
Decision-makers	Will be involved in the strategic direction, compliance and funding of EOSC.	National, Regional or Local Government Agencies Research Funding Bodies

Table 4 - EOSC Primary Stakeholder Roles

In addition, there are some additional roles which are covered by the above stakeholders, but worth explicitly articulating – these are detailed in Table 5.

Supplementary Role	Description	Relationship to Primary Roles
Value-added providers	Many stakeholders (including e-infrastructures, research infrastructures, VREs etc.) will consume services and resources from some providers to provide value added services and resources to other consumers.	Within both Provider and Consumer roles
Funders	Provides funding for research on a local, national or international level	Sub-role within Decision-makers
Policy-makers	Regulates policy at a local, national or regional level.	Sub-role within Decision-makers

Table 5 - EOsc Supplementary Stakeholder Roles

5.2. Resources

5.2.1. Definition of EOsc Resource

EOsc Resource = Services + Data + People

At the centre of EOsc are the EOsc Resources themselves – the EOsc Resources cover the range of services and facilities needed to support Open Science and Research. These include technical services such as analytics and computational services, cloud services, thematic services tuned to particular research disciplines, e-infrastructure and middleware services such as access identity management; but also knowledge resources such as datasets, storage, digital library and archives; access services such as a service catalogue and portals; scientific instruments and facilities; and facilitation activities such as training, software development support and consultancy.

5.2.2. Compliance and Compatibility

It is envisaged that most of the EOsc resources will be fully *compliant* with the Rules of Participation and, where applicable, compatible with the technical architecture. However, it is likely that, at least initially, there will be resources which are not fully *compliant* but are merely technically *compatible* with the EOsc but are still of value to the EOsc Consumers. Such resources might meet the needs of specific disciplines only, or may be currently in the process of becoming compliant, or transitioning into the EOsc.

There may also be some resources which may not be fully technically *compatible* with EOsc resources nor fully *compliant* with the Rules of Participation, but which nevertheless are of value to EOsc consumers. These would still be usable by EOsc consumers as recommended by the HLEG that “*It should be clear that non-EOsc approved players are free to explore any role in the Open Science ecosystem they wish, even if they do not adhere to the Rules of Participation. They will just not be able to brand their services as EOsc approved/certified*”.

This is illustrated below in Figure 6. The EOscpilot has co-developed an initial set of Rules of Participation²⁹ with the community, as well as developed a technical architecture³⁰ which provides more precise definitions of *compliant* and *compatible*.

²⁹ See “D2.5: Recommendations for a minimal set of Rules of Participation” at <https://www.eosc-pilot.eu/content/d25-recommendations-minimal-set-rules-participation>

³⁰ See “D5.1: Initial EOsc Service Architecture” at <https://www.eosc-pilot.eu/content/d51-initial-eosc-service-architecture>

Figure 6 - EOSC Resource Model: Rules of Participation

5.2.3. Open Market and Financial Flows

To function, there will need to be some **Core Resources** underpinning the EOSC analogous to services underpinning the internet, such as domain naming services etc. Such resources might include the EOSC service catalogue, access and identity management, etc. The need for **Core Resources** was also identified by the OSPSP EOSC Working Group³¹ whose definition is “set of services and processes that are needed to integrate and enable access to the various resources federated in the EOSC”. The **Core Resources** will need to be directly commissioned and financially compensated. The **Executive** should have the primary responsibility, in discussion with the **Strategic** and **Stakeholder** layers, to determine the requirements of these core resources, and decide how they will be delivered.

In order to meet the objective of “free at the point of use”, resource provision will need to receive **Compensation** and financial support by other means³². Various models of this compensation could include contribution of resources by member states and institutions, direct commission by the **Executive** or compensation based on usage using mechanism in the Framework Programmes (such as Transnational or Virtual Access instruments³³) or new mechanisms such as “Cloud Coins” or other credit mechanisms. Facilities and services to enable such credit mechanisms will need to be provided by the EOSC **Core Resources**.

To ensure that the EOSC remains relevant and to encourage innovation, it will be necessary to identify any **Resource Gaps** which may exist in provision. Gaps may be identified by the **Stakeholder** or **Executive** layers and notified to the **Executive** and **Strategic** layers. The **Executive** will need to develop mechanisms to fill any such gaps in provision, either by directly incentivising the development of new resources and services or through advocacy to the Strategic layer and the Framework Programmes. This may also need to include incentives to transition existing resources into the EOSC, by providing mechanisms to help resource providers meet the technical requirements and Rules of Participation.

To ensure that EOSC remains an **Open Market** “open to all players, public and private, European and non-European” (as required by the first HLEG report³⁴), there may also be resources within EOSC which will not be directly compensated through EOSC, but through other means (including commercial

³¹ https://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/pdf/ospp_euro_open_science_cloud_report-.pdf

³² See “D2.4: Recommendations and prerequisites to realise EOSC as a sustainable ecosystem”. D2.4 was awaiting publication at the time of publication of this report. It will be available from the EOSCpilot website at <https://www.eoscipilot.eu/media/deliverables>.

³³ http://www.rich2020.eu/tas_calls/about

³⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/pdf/realising_the_european_open_science_cloud_2016.pdf

resources paid directly by researchers or their institutions), but which nevertheless meet the requirements to be EOSC *compliant* or *compatible* and are of value to the community.

In summary (as illustrated in Figure 7):

- An EOSC Resource is *Compliant* if it meets the Rules of Participation for the EOSC.
- An EOSC Resource is *Compatible* if it meets the technical requirements as defined by the EOSC technical architecture.
- Some resources which are needed to integrate and enable access to the various resources federated in the EOSC will be *Core Resources* (which, by definition, will need to be *Compliant*).
- *Compliant* resources will be eligible to be part of EOSC; resources neither *Compliant* nor *Compatible* will be external to EOSC; *Compatible* only resources might be borderline (if, for instance, they are transitioning into EOSC).
- EOSC resources (both commercial and non-commercial) might be compensated for their usage via mechanisms within EOSC; some EOSC resources might be funded via other means, including commercial models.

Figure 7 - EOSC Resource Model: Economics

6. GOVERNANCE MODEL

6.1. Community Lead Governance

Ultimately, the governance model should allow the engagement of all stakeholders, in all stakeholder roles, such that they are peers in the decision making for EOSC. For this, EOSC can borrow from Community Governance in the public sector as typically used for local government or social community initiatives. In this context, Community governance refers to the processes for making all the decisions and plans that affect life in the community, whether made by public or private organisations or by citizens. To be effective, it considers three core community skills of *engaging citizens*, *measuring results*, and *getting things done* in order to help people and organisations make decisions about what actions to take in a community and to measure their impact and effectiveness. The interaction between these “skills” is shown in Figure 8.

Effective Community Governance Model

1 Community Problems Solving:

Aligns “Engaging Citizens” and “Getting Things Done.”

2 Organizations Managing for Results:

Aligns “Measuring Results” and “Getting Things Done.”

3 Citizens Reaching for Results:

Aligns “Engaging Citizens” and “Measuring Results.”

4 Communities Governing for Results:

Aligns all three core skills.

Figure 8 - Effective Community Governance³⁵

The EOSC Declaration³⁶ defined three governance layers:

- **Institutional** – including EU Member States and the European Commission.
- **Executive/Operational** – including a governance board at the executive level and relevant working committees.
- **Advisory** – including a stakeholder forum.

These map very closely to the skills in the community governance model above. In this model, the **Advisory** layer from the declaration would involve the *engaging citizens* skills to determine the scientific and technical needs of the users. The term “Advisory” is meant, in this context, to concern engaging with all stakeholders. It is important that stakeholders are, and feel that they are, peers in the decision-making process. They should perform a role that is both advisory and guiding - it should provide strong guidance and direction (not just advisory) to the Strategic and Executive layers. Within the EC Staff Working Document³⁷ and the Second HLEG Report³⁸ this is referred to as the **Stakeholder** layer.

³⁵ http://www.rtmteam.net/page.php?pageID=25§ion=overview_of_ecg

³⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/pdf/eosc_declaration.pdf

³⁷ http://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/pdf/swd_2018_83_f1_staff_working_paper_en.pdf

³⁸ <https://publications.europa.eu/en/web/eu-law-and-publications/publication-detail/-/publication/5253a1af-ee10-11e8-b690-01aa75ed71a1>

The declaration's **Institutional** layer defines the strategic objectives and measures the impact and effectiveness of EOOSC against these objectives and so would principally map to the *Measuring Results* skill. Within the EC Staff Working Document and the Second HLEG Report this is referred to as the **Strategic** layer.

Finally, the **Executive\Operational** layer would map to the *Getting Things Done* skill by ensuring that the EOOSC delivers to meet the needs of the stakeholders through the strategic objectives set by the Institutional layer. Within the EC Staff Working Document and the Second HLEG Report this is referred to as the **Executive** layer.

These layers are illustrated in Figure 9.

Figure 9 - EOOSC Governance Layers

The intersections of these skills and layers are important in delivering an effective governance structure for EOOSC. The **Stakeholder** layer determines within its communities' best practice, standards, rules of participation, in effect addressing the recommendations of "*Guidance only where guidance is due*" and "*Define Rules of Participation for service provision in the EOOSC*" from the HLEG group report, as well as the scientific and technical requirements of the EOOSC. This forms a discussion and interaction with the **Strategic** layer, articulates the strategic objectives for the EOOSC, and the metrics to measure how well the EOOSC delivers against these objectives. This leads to an interaction between the **Strategic** and **Executive** layers to determine how the EOOSC is provisioned and commissioned to meet these objectives. Finally, there is a feedback loop between the **Stakeholder** and **Executive** on how well the EOOSC is meeting the communities' needs, standards and practices, and a report back from the **Executive** to the **Strategic** layer on how effective the EOOSC is meeting the strategy, and how effective the strategic goals are at capturing the real needs of the communities. This is outlined in Figure 10.

Figure 10 - Community Governance Model for EOSC

6.2. Decision Flow

The overall decision flow between these layers is outlined in Figure 11 (the structures within the layers is elaborated on in the next section on Governance Structure).

- The **Stakeholder** layer would allow the stakeholders to determine the requirements, policies and Rules of Participation, and make proposals on how these could be met to the **Strategic** Layer. The **Strategic** layer would review, agree and prioritise these proposals and requirements to form the strategic vision and objectives of the EOSC.
- The **Executive** layer would be responsible for ensuring that the EOSC meets this vision and these objectives by: commissioning Core resource as required; commissioning new Supported resources as required; ensuring that Supported resources are properly compensated; and ensuring that the resources within EOSC are both compliant and meet the strategic objectives.
- The **Stakeholder** layer would also communicate to the **Executive** how well the EOSC is meeting their requirements at an operational level, and the **Executive** would report this against the strategic objective to the Strategic layer.

For example, a scientific discipline (or disciplines) within the **Stakeholder** layer might define data interoperability and re-use principles for data within their domains. The **Strategic** layer would translate this into strategic objectives and requirements for resource within EOSC which handle such data. The **Executive** would have responsibility for ensuring such resources existed within EOSC, and would receive input from the **Stakeholder** layer on how well these resources are in enabling data interoperability and re-use. Alternatively, communities within the **Stakeholder** layer might identify key areas where training and support are required, the **Strategic** layer would again translate these to objectives, the **Executive** would ensure that there were resources within EOSC to meet these training and support requirements, and the **Stakeholder** would report how effective they are.

Figure 11 - Governance Decision Flow

7. GOVERNANCE STRUCTURE

7.1. Overall Structure

The European Interoperability Framework³⁹ defines four types of interoperability:

- **Legal Interoperability** is about ensuring that organisations operating under different legal frameworks, policies and strategies are capable to work together.
- **Organisational Interoperability** refers to the way in which public administrations align their business processes, responsibilities and expectations to achieve commonly agreed and mutually beneficial goals.
- **Semantic Interoperability** ensures that the precise format and meaning of exchanged data and information is preserved and understood throughout exchanges between parties.
- **Technical Interoperability** covers the applications and infrastructures linking systems, services and resources. Aspects of technical interoperability include interface specifications, interconnection services, data integration services, data presentation and exchange, and secure communication protocols.

Figure 12 - European Interoperability Layers

The Governance structure is derived from the European Interoperability Framework with some slight re-interpretation of the four layers, as illustrated in Figure 12; within the context of EOsc, **Legal Interoperability** also includes Policy interoperability as well as Rules of Participation for EOsc; and **Organisational Interoperability** includes both Strategy and Funding.

Currently, the Rules of Participation (RoP)⁴⁰ are broad and can cover different aspects. It currently focuses on rules and guidelines for resource organisations to promote and offer resources through the EOsc Portal. In the evolution of the EOsc Portal, the Governance model will need to address how Resource Organisations might need to define their Rules of Participation when they may appear in many different services catalogues (e.g. at a national or institutional level) with different RoP whilst remaining “compliant” within the EOsc Portal's presentation of services and other offerings.

³⁹ https://ec.europa.eu/isa2/eif_en

⁴⁰ See “D2.5: Recommendations for a minimal set of Rules of Participation” at <https://www.eoscpilot.eu/content/d25-recommendations-minimal-set-rules-participation>

Figure 13 - Overall Governance Structure

Legal, the resource allocation aspects of **Organisational**, and **Technical** would form three pillars within the Stakeholder layer, **Semantic** (in terms of operational implementation of all the EIF layers) would be the responsibility of the Executive which would mirror the three pillars of the Stakeholder layer. Other strategic aspects of **Organisational** as well as oversight of all EIF layers would rest within the Strategic layer. The overview of these layer and pillars is shown in Figure 13, and outlined in Table 6.

Each of these three layers would have a coordinating Board with strong reporting lines between these Boards. However, it is anticipated that there would be other liaison between the layers – in particular, between the Stakeholder and Executive layers as outlined above.

Strategic	The Governance Framework foresees EOSC growing beyond Europe and the Strategic Layer growing to include representation from all countries and funders wishing to join and support the EOSC.
Stakeholder	<p>The Stakeholder will include three pillars representing the Technical, Organisational (as regards to resource allocation and demand) and Legal (including policy alignment) layers of the EIF. These would have close working relationships with the relevant pillars of the Executive.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A Technical Oversight Committee to agree and monitor quality standards for the EOSC Resources – this will be informed by research community specific sub-committees. • A Research Resource Demand Committee to have oversight in how EOSC resources are allocated – this will be informed by research community specific panels. • A Policy and Rules of Participation Oversight Committee to recommend research policy alignment – this will be informed by research community specific sub-committees. <p>There would also be an Ethics and Legal Advisory Board within the Legal pillar reporting directly to the Stakeholder Engagement Board and with close liaison to the Executive Board</p> <p>It is anticipated that there will be working groups within the stakeholder forum both within these pillars, and cross-cutting working groups, to work on specific aspects of EOSC, in particular for determining future resources and developments. These would typically be time limited.</p>
Executive	<p>The Executive will include representation of those providing EOSC resources – both core resources essential for the federation of EOSC, and specific and specialised resources. It will include three similar pillars to the Stakeholder layer - essentially being providing (in EIF terms) the Semantic (i.e. Operational) implementation of the three pillars in the Stakeholder layer:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A Technical Operational (Semantic) pillar ensuring that EOSC resources meet the needs and standards of the communities consisting of the EOSC System Steering Committee, Service Portfolio Management Committee and EOSC System

	<p>Executive Committee as defined in the EOSC Architecture and Service Management Framework.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An Organisational Operational (Semantic) pillar including a Resource Allocation Committee to ensure that communities have appropriate access to scarce resources based on research excellence and impact, and a Financial and Commercial Steering Committee to oversee financial flows and procurement of resources. • A Legal Operational (Semantic) pillar including a Policy Alignment Steering Committee to ensure necessary alignment of resource provider policies both between providers and with national and international policies.
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Table 6 - Governance Structure Layers

7.2. Strategic Governance

Figure 14 - Strategic Governance

As the Strategic Governance (Figure 14) should involve the representatives of national policy and national funding agencies, we believe that the European Commission and its existing structures should inform the exact nature of this structure. It is possible, for example, that this might be a task for an existing structure such as the ERAC. However, we do foresee that the EOSC might grow beyond Europe, and hence the governing board should include representation from all countries wishing to join and support the EOSC – hence the reference to **EOSC member countries** rather than **EU member countries**.

7.3. Stakeholder Governance

7.3.1. Governance Structure

Figure 15 - Stakeholder Governance

A recommendation from the EOSC 2nd HLEG is to have the Stakeholders Forum move its focus in 2019 to a more user-centred approach in order to guarantee a “**Voice of the Users**”, including practical cases of how EOSC is making a difference to “how things were done previously” for them in their thematic areas.

The Stakeholder forum (Figure 15) would have three key pillars, approximately mapping to the EIF layers of **Technical**, **Organisational** and **Legal** respectively:

- A **Technical Oversight Committee** to agree and monitor quality standards for the EOSC Resources. It would handle quality assignment requests, and quality measure monitoring,

liaising closely with the EOSC System Steering Committee and overseeing the scientific discipline technical subcommittees. The team will rely on internationally set standards that can be audited by external parties and relies on their input for quality assignment. They will also keep track of resource and service quality monitoring. It would be informed by research community specific sub-committees, which would define and check quality measures on behalf of research communities. This would be formed by any community that can sustain such an effort for longer periods of time. They will report to the EOSC TC but assign and maintain quality measures independently.

- A **Research Resource Demand Committee** to have oversight in how EOSC resources are allocated – this will be informed by research community specific panels.
- A **Policy and Rules of Participation Oversight Committee** to recommend research policy alignment – this will be informed by research community specific sub-committees. This would subsume the stakeholder policy related aspects of the Policy Standing Committee proposed in the EOSCpilot policy recommendations⁴¹ after the initial implementation period of the EOSC.

In addition, the **Legal** pillar would also include an Ethics and Legal Advisory Board⁴² whose mandate would be to identify ethical and legal and policy issues to review the actions of EOSC from an ethical and legal perspective, as well as acting as the source of further ethical and legal initiatives within the organisation. This would sit in the Stakeholder forum, reporting to the Stakeholder Engagement Board to ensure its independence but would have a close advisory and liaison line into the Executive Board.

7.3.2. Supporting Structures

The European Interoperability Framework includes the concept of overlapping domains, and this can be used to understand how different communities would need to interact. This can be applied to scientific and research domains, comparable to the Domain Interoperability Frameworks in Figure 16. Each scientific domain has its own best practices and standards, and the role of EOSC is to determine and coordinate the overlap between these different domains. In this way, it provides “guidance only where guidance is due”. It also applies to how different providers and intermediaries should engage with the EOSC Governance, in that it is the intersection of practices and standards between International, National and Local provision of resources which is important for EOSC. This is the principle behind the various subcommittees and panels within the three pillars.

⁴¹ See “D3.6: Final Policy Recommendations” at <https://www.eoscipilot.eu/content/d36-final-policy-recommendations>

⁴² In order to implement Action 1.4 of “D3.6: Final Policy Recommendations” - the Ethics and Legal Advisory Board might be established within the Executive during the interim implementation phase of EOSC and then transition into the Stakeholder Forum.

Figure 16 - European Interoperability Framework Domains of Domains

There are a number of models used in other organisations which were considered in structuring the Stakeholder Model. Examples include the IETF (for internet standards), RDA (for Research Data Management), WISE Community (for e-infrastructure security), OASIS (for Web Service and metadata standards) and W3C (for Web standards). The main differences between these concern their legal and financial structures, but in terms of governance, they can broadly be modelled to two or more of the levels outlined in Figure 17.

Figure 17 - Stakeholders Forum Organisational Model

This model includes:

- Oversight, e.g. a board or committees that agrees the rules of membership, engagement and processes and acts as the key contact point with the Strategic and Executive layers.
- Standing Groups, e.g. for Thematic Areas, either based on the Interoperability Contexts, the Stakeholder Roles or broad scientific or infrastructure domains, dealing with specific thematic domains.
- Working Groups, that are time based, work on specific areas with the priorities determined by the Stakeholder forum governance in conjunction with the Strategic and Executive layers of the EOsc Governance.
- Emergent Topic Groups discuss new activities that may lead to working groups.

Table 7 illustrates how various community organisations map to this model.

	IETF	RDA	WISE	OASIS	W3C
Oversight	Internet Architecture Board	Council, Technical Advisory Board, Organisational Advisory Board	Steering Committee	Board, Technical Advisory Board	Technical Architecture Group, Advisory Board
Standing Groups	Internet Engineering Steering Group and Area Directors	Interest Groups	N/A	Member Sections	Interest Groups, Business and Community Groups
Working Groups	Working Groups	Working Groups	Working Groups	Technical Committees	Working Groups
Emergent Topic Groups	Birds of a Feather (BOF) session at an IETF meeting	Birds of a Feather (BOF) session at an RDA meeting	N/A	Proposed Technical Committee Discussion List	Discussion Lists

Table 7 - Community Organisation Structures

Within the Stakeholder Mode, ‘Oversight’ is provided by the Stakeholder Engagement Board and ‘Standing Groups’ by the various pillars. However, it is also foreseen that the Stakeholder Model needs time limited working groups to ensure future development and evolution of the EOsc.

In terms of organisational or legal structure, the Stakeholder engagement forum should be open to all stakeholders and should borrow from structures such as RDA or open source foundation models.

Any structure for the Stakeholders Forum should use the key principles of ISO 38500 (Governance of IT) as guiding principles, namely:

- **Responsibility** – Stakeholders know their responsibilities, both in terms of demand and supply of EOsc resources and have the authority to meet them.
- **Strategy** – Business and funding strategies should be aligned with technological possibilities, and all the technologies and resources within EOsc within an organisation should support the EOsc objectives and strategies.
- **Acquisition** – all investments must be made based on a research case with regular monitoring in place to assess whether the assumptions still hold.
- **Performance** – the performance of EOsc resources should lead to research benefits and therefore it is necessary that the resources support research properly.

- **Conformance** – EOSC resources should help to ensure that research processes comply with legislation and regulations; EOSC resource themselves must also comply with legal requirements and agreed internal rules.
- **Human behaviour** – policies, practices and decisions respects human behaviour and acknowledges the needs of all the people in the process.

Underpinning this, there may need to be a legal structure such as a charity, and a Secretariat or other supporting agency which might be shared with the Executive, however, the independence of the Stakeholder Engagement Forum is paramount.

7.4. Executive Governance

7.4.1. Governance Structure

Figure 18 - Executive Governance

The Executive Governance (Figure 18) would have three key pillars, approximately mapping to the EIF layers of **Technical**, **Organisational** and **Legal** respectively, in a **Semantic** (i.e. Operational sense), as outlined in Table 8:

Technical + Semantic Pillar	<p>EOSC System Steering Committee</p> <p>Committee of System Owners as defined in the EOsc Architecture⁴³ i.e. those responsible / accountable for the establishment and maintenance of the EOsc System. Steers the EOsc System by setting the key goals and directions. Its tasks include overseeing the development of the EOsc Service Portfolio.</p> <p>EOsc Service Portfolio Management Committee</p> <p>As defined in the EOsc Service Management Framework⁴⁴ - responsible for the definition and development of the EOsc Service Portfolio - the internal list of EOsc Services and Resources including those in preparation, live and discontinued.</p> <p>EOsc System Executive Committee</p> <p>Committee of Top System Managers as defined in the EOsc Technical Architecture i.e. those responsible / accountable for the overall operation of the EOsc System. Guarantees that the EOsc System is behaving according to its established goal and directions.</p>
Organisational + Semantic Pillar	<p>Resource Allocation Committee</p> <p>To ensure that communities have appropriate access to scarce resources based on research excellence and impact.</p> <p>Finance & Commercial Steering Committee</p> <p>Oversee financial aspects of EOsc including procuring and supporting key EOsc resources.</p>
Legal + Semantic Pillar	<p>Policy Alignment Steering Committee</p> <p>To ensure necessary alignment of service and resource provider policies, both between providers and with national and international policies. This would subsume the operational policy related aspects of the Policy Standing Committee proposed in the EOscpilot policy recommendations⁴⁵ after the initial implementation period of the EOsc.</p>

Table 8 - Executive Governance Pillars

7.4.2. Supporting Structures

There are broadly three potential models for the EOsc to commission and provide financial support to Core and Supported EOsc Resources. Each model can be regarded as both an intermediate step towards more complicated models as well a potential end state. Each model may be supported by a legal structure (such as an ERIC) and a secretariat or other supporting agency which might be shared with the Stakeholder Engagement Forum.

⁴³ See "D5.1: Initial EOsc Service Architecture" at <https://www.eosc-pilot.eu/content/d51-initial-eosc-service-architecture>

⁴⁴ See "D5.3: EOsc Federated Service Management Framework" at <https://www.eosc-pilot.eu/content/d53-eosc-federated-service-management-framework>

⁴⁵ See "D3.6: Final Policy Recommendations" at <https://www.eosc-pilot.eu/content/d36-final-policy-recommendations>

Lightweight Delivery Model

The Executive commissions and pays for (either directly or through some compensatory mechanism) Core and Supported resources from international, national, institutional and commercial providers through existing mechanisms (e.g. Framework Programme instruments such as Virtual Access) as shown in Figure 19. The pros and cons of this approach are outline in Table 9.

Figure 19 - Light Weight Executive Delivery Model

Pros	Cons
Minimal Impact on present structures	Little impact of possibility to change resources of present providers Slow change cycle Would need collaboration agreements
Maintains existing entry points	
Maintained Subsidiarity principle (that access should be through local or national institutions)	
Fast to implement	
Present funding mechanisms can be used	
Flexible and agile in terms of providers	

Table 9 - Light Weight Executive Delivery Model: Pros and Cons

Commissioning Authority

The establishment of a new entity (possibly a legal structure such as an ERIC) that would have responsibility for commissioning (e.g. contracting or framework agreements) Core and Supported Resources, as shown in Figure 20. The pros and cons of this approach are outline in Table 10.

Figure 20 - Commissioning Authority

Pros	Cons
Clean interface between funder and provider	Require major agreement between Member States and European Commission
From providers' perspective, a new business opportunity	Slow to implement
An ERIC structure would allow additional mechanisms for Member State contributions	Breaks Subsidiarity Principle by providing centralised provision of national or local resources

Table 10 - Commissioning Authority: Pros and Cons

Delivery Authority

The establishment of a new entity (possibly a legal structure such as an ERIC) that would have responsibility for delivering Core and Supported Resources, either directly or through contracting or framework agreements with third parties, as show in Figure 21. The pros and cons of this approach are outline in Table 11.

Figure 21 - Delivery Authority

Pros	Cons
Organisational integration between public European e-infrastructures	Artificially tight integration of very different business models Very long time to implement Needs strong coordination of national resources

Table 11 - Delivery Authority: Pros and Cons

8. GOVERNANCE TRANSITION

The European Commission’s staff working document "Implementation Roadmap for the European Open Science Cloud"⁴⁶ outlines an interim governance structure for the initial implementation phase of the EOSC:

Figure 22 - Staff Working Document Governance Structure

The report of the Second High Level Expert Group on the Open Science Cloud (Prompting an EOSC in Practice)⁴⁷, provides an alternative overview of this interim governance structure:

Figure 23 - Second HLEG Report Governance Overview

There are three main differences between these this interim governance structure and the framework described in this document:

⁴⁶ http://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/pdf/swd_2018_83_f1_staff_working_paper_en.pdf

⁴⁷ <https://publications.europa.eu/en/web/eu-law-and-publications/publication-detail/-/publication/5253a1af-ee10-11e8-b690-01aa75ed71a1>

- As regards the **Strategic** layer, the Staff Working Document is very careful to detail the EOSC Board - they are the decision-making body and they also decide who is in the Executive board and who is in the Stakeholder layer.
- The Staff Working Document sees the working groups as part of the **Executive** layer, whereas the EOSCpilot model sees these as part of the **Stakeholder** layer with a much greater independence for the Stakeholder layer to self-organise and self-populate.
- The Staff Working Document has very little to say about the **Stakeholder** layer apart from its role in the Strategic in determining its membership, apparently minimizing the importance of the stakeholder forum. The EOSCpilot framework emphasizes their importance puts a lot of emphasis on the relationships and information flow, the communication between the layers.

Table 12 presents a more detailed comparison.

	EC Staff Working Document Governance Structure	EOSCpilot Governance Framework
STRATEGIC	Members: MS + EC (DG RTD and DG CNECT)	Members: MS + EC
	Function: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ensures effective supervision of the implementation - decides strategic orientation of EOSC and commitment and financial support - institutional and political oversight - approves members of Executive Board - approves annual workplan - assesses progress of EOSC implementation - coordinates with other MS/EC initiatives 	Function: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - defines strategic objectives - measure the impact and effectiveness of EOSC
EXECUTIVE	Members: max. 10 chosen by the EOSC Board from ESFRI infrastructures, eInfrastructures, scientific organisations, university associations etc.	Members: not defined
	Function: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ensures proper implementation and accountability - proposes the strategy & workplan drafts the Rules of Participation - oversees and steers the implementation of the workplan together with the working groups (WGs) - monitors the implementation of EOSC (by 2020) - proposes how to broaden the user base to public sector and industry 	Function: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ensures EOSC delivers to meet the needs of the Stakeholders

	EC Staff Working Document Governance Structure	EOSCpilot Governance Framework
STAKEHOLDERS	Members: broad participation by organisations\institutions\communities (possibly decided by EOSC Board), single representative per organisation\institution\community – requires adherence to the principles of EOSC	Members: individuals including organisations\institutional representatives; multiple sub-forums (consumers, providers etc.)
	Function: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Intelligence gathering and Consultative role - Expertise but no decision-making body 	Function: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recommends\proposes within communities best practices, standards, Rules of Participation - Recommends\proposes “Rules of Participation for service provision in the EOSC” from HLEG group report - Recommends\proposes scientific and technical requirements of the EOSC

Table 12 - Governance Crosswalk

Despite the differences, there is a clear evolutionary path between the model in the staff working model and the longer-term model described later in this document, with the Stakeholder Forum evolving to become more independent and able to take a stronger role in determining the direction of EOSC to ensure that it meets its users’ needs, and, for the working groups as they move from an implementation focus to move across under the remit of the Stakeholder Forum to ensure independence between the advisory and delivery roles. This is illustrated in Figure 24. In the meantime, the Executive evolves to take a much more operational role, taking advice and input from the Stakeholder layer. Its supporting Coordination Structure would evolve into one of the delivery models outlined in the framework as illustrated in Figure 25.

Figure 24 - Governance Transition

EOSCpilot
post-2020

EC Staff Working Document
up to 2020

Figure 25 - Delivery Transition

9. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

This document outlines a stakeholder driven governance framework for the long-term management and oversight of EOSC. It forms a natural evolution of the implementation-phase governance structure established by the European Commission by:

1. Extending the Executive to include standing groups performing important roles in terms of Legal (including policy), Organisational (including funding), Semantic (in terms of operational management), and Technical interoperability (as defined by the European Interoperability Framework) of EOSC resources.
2. Establishing a shadow structure to the Executive within the Stakeholder forum, to ensure that the Executive delivers an EOSC fit for its end users, and to develop metrics and policies which meet user requirements and demands.
3. Moving time-based working groups from the Executive to the Stakeholder forum as the focus of these working groups change from initial implementation issues to focus on the longer-term future development and evolution of EOSC.

This document has been placed in the public domain on github at the following locations, so that it can be owned and further developed by the EOSC community:

- **Reading version:** <https://europeanopensciencecloud.github.io/Governance/>
- **Editable version:** <https://github.com/EuropeanOpenScienceCloud/Governance/>

10. GLOSSARY

Term	Explanation
EOSC	The European Open Science Cloud promoted by the European Commission to provide all researchers, innovators, companies and citizens with seamless access to an open-by-default, efficient and cross-disciplinary environment for storing, accessing, reusing data, tools, publications and any EOSC Resource for research, innovation and educational purposes. EOSC is implemented by the EOSC System and governed by the EOSC Governance .
EC	European Commission
EIF	European Interoperability Framework
EOSC Core Resource	EOSC Resources, services and processes that are needed to integrate and enable access to the various resources federated in the EOSC.
EOSC Resource	Any asset made available (by means of the EOSC system and according to the EOSC Rules of Participation) to EOSC System Users to perform a process useful to deliver value in the context of the EOSC . EOSC Resources include services, datasets, software, support, training, consultancy or any other asset.
European Interoperability Framework	EC framework giving specific guidance on how to set up interoperable digital public services.
H2020	Horizon 2020 is the biggest EU Research and Innovation programme ever with nearly €80 billion of funding available over 7 years (2014 to 2020) – in addition to the private investment that this money will attract. It promises more breakthroughs, discoveries and world-firsts by taking great ideas from the lab to the market.
HLEG	High Level Expert Group
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
OASIS	OASIS is a non-profit consortium that drives the development, convergence and adoption of open standards for the global information society.
Open Innovation	According to EC, the basic premise of Open Innovation is to introduce more actors in the innovation process so that knowledge can circulate more freely and be transformed into products and services that create new markets, fostering a stronger culture of entrepreneurship.
Open Science	The movement to make scientific research, data and dissemination accessible to all levels of an inquiring society, amateur or professional.

Term	Explanation
OSPP	Open Science Policy Platform
Principles of Engagement	See Rules of Participation
Project partners	The EOSCpilot project partners
RACI	RACI is an acronym that stands for responsible, accountable, consulted and informed. A RACI chart is a matrix of all the activities or decision-making authorities undertaken in an organisation set against all the people or roles.
RDA	Research Data Alliance
Research Infrastructures	Research infrastructures (RIs) are facilities, resources and services used by the science community to conduct research and foster innovation.
Rules of Engagement	See Rules of Participation
Rules of Participation	The principles defined by the EOSC Governance to drive the processes enacting an actor to play the role of EOSC System User (and any specialization of it). Previously referred to as “Rules of Engagement” or “Principles of Engagement” in earlier communications and reports.
SMEs	Small and medium-sized enterprises
Standing Committee\Group	A long-term committee or group with a long term or indefinite objectives and terms of reference.
Subsidiarity Principle	The principle that the idea that political action should be taken as close to the citizen as possible. This means that in an instance where the EU and a member state are both able to take action, action should ordinarily be taken by the member state Within the research context, this means that access to resources (scientific, IT, etc.) should be should be through local or national institutions.
VREs	Virtual Research Environments
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
Working Committee\Group	A short-term committee or group with a defined time limited term of reference.